

777372 - RESOLUTE

Research Empowerment on Solute Carriers

**WP1 – Generation of
reagents and cell lines to
allow system-wide study of
the SLC family**

D1.2 SLC KO cell lines

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Abstract

RESOLUTE aims to unlock the therapeutic potential of solute carriers (SLCs) in a systematic and coordinated effort. To reach this goal, loss- and gain-of-function studies using SLC knock-out (KO) and overexpression (OE) cell models are crucial. To create suitable KO cell lines, we selected a human cancer cell line panel in which about 80% of the originally 426 proposed targets are endogenously expressed. By lentiviral delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 vectors, we were able to generate single-cell clones with loss-of-function mutations for approximately 300 SLCs. For the majority of these targets (93%) at least two independent KO clones were derived. For quality control and cell line characterization, we performed mycoplasma and sterility testing as well as whole RNA sequencing (RNA-seq). Within the RESOLUTE consortium, these cell lines are mainly used in genetic interaction studies, binder generation and validation, and the generation of rescue cell models where genetically deleted SLCs are re-expressed in the KO clones (KO-OE cell lines). We anticipate that the data generated using these reagents as well as the cell lines themselves will have a highly significant and broad impact on SLC research.

Methods

Lentiviral CRISPR/Cas9 KO vectors:

To introduce frame-shifting mutations into SLC genes, we designed and cloned one sgRNA per target for all 446 annotated SLCs into the pLentiCRISPRv2 vector (Addgene). Additionally, we used a set of 347 modified pLentiCRISPRv2 vectors that has been previously used in our lab (Girardi et al., unpublished). For targets where no gRNA from these two collections could be functionally validated, three more sets of gRNAs (96, 32 and 22 gRNAs) were successively designed and used in further attempts to generate KO clones.

KO pool generation and single cell cloning:

As no human cell expresses all SLCs, a limited number of cell lines covering as many SLCs as possible was needed to generate KO clones in a large-scale effort. To identify suitable cellular models to generate KO clones in a large-scale effort, we first selected a panel of six human cancer cell lines: HCT116, 1321N1, LS180, HuH-7, SK-MEL-28, MDA-MB-468. The panel was chosen to have at least one cell line with endogenous expression (TPM > 1) for about 80% of the known SLCs. However, during the course of the project, two of these cell lines (SK-MEL-28 and MDA-MB-468) turned out to be extremely difficult to subclone and for the HuH-7 line it took up to several months to expand single cells to monoclonal cell lines. Since HCT116 was one of the fastest growing and the easiest to subclone cell line, we selected this cell line for all targets that were not expressed more than 5-fold higher in another cell line. 1321N1, LS180 and HuH-7 cell lines were chosen if endogenous expression was at least 5-fold higher than in HCT116.

293T packaging cells were transfected with pLentiCRISPR vectors and lentiviral packaging constructs to produce infectious viral particles. Generally, new gRNA vectors were tested in HEK cells to assess their editing efficiency before they were used to generate KO clones. For this a part of the viral supernatant was transduced into HEK JumpIn cells and cells were collected after antibiotic selection. Genomic DNA was harvested and editing efficiency was determined by NGS as described below. Generally, we required at least 60% edited alleles in the HEK pools for a gRNA to be considered as experimentally validated. The remaining part of the virus was then used to transduce one of the six selected cancer cell lines. After antibiotic selection, KO pools were frozen or immediately used for single cell cloning. Depending on the used cancer cell line, single cell clones were generated either by limited dilution seeding or FACS. Single cells were sorted into 96-well dishes and expanded for 2-3 weeks before freezing and harvesting genomic DNA for genotyping. Usually, we aimed to generate 12 single-cell clones per KO pool to have a high chance of identifying at least two KO clones per target. The remaining clones were frozen directly on the 96-plate and kept at -80°C as backup in case more clones were needed for genotyping.

To generate WT controls that underwent the same procedures as our KO clones, we transduced all parental cell lines with gRNAs targeting the Renilla luciferase gene which is absent in the human genome. Selection and single cell sorting of these cell lines was performed as for KO clones to match them as close as possible. Per parental cell line, 2-8 Renilla WT clones were generated as controls for various assays.

Genotyping procedure:

The vast majority of generated clones were genotyped using an NGS-based approach. For this, a 200-600 bp fragment containing the gRNA cut site was amplified with primer that contain partial Illumina adapter sequences as 5'overhangs. Using a universal set of Illumina barcoding primer (12 x i7 barcodes and 8 x i5 barcodes), we then introduced unique barcode combinations as well as the remaining part of the Illumina adapters to the PCR products. Samples were then purified and multiplexed to assemble the Illumina library. In theory, 96 clones could be genotyped with the available barcode combinations. Since also the sequence of the PCR amplicon itself can be used to demultiplex the NGS reads, up to several thousand clones could be multiplexed in one sequencing run. However, for practical reasons we usually multiplexed and sequenced only 350-450 samples together in one HiSeq run. For the analysis of the NGS genotyping data, we developed a custom software (CREScant) that allows the automatic detection of frame-shifting and deletions and insertions in our genes of interest. As an alternative genotyping approach (which was also used to confirm the genotype of about 50 KO clones after expansion), we sequenced the amplified PCR products by Sanger sequencing and determined mutations using the ICE tool (Synthego).

After KO clones were identified, the original freeze stocks were thawed, expanded, and used for quality control and a set of new freeze stocks. If more than two KO clones were identified for one target, we chose up to four clones for expansion. However, only two of the clones were further analysed while the rest was frozen as backup clones.

Quality control and multi-parameter cell line characterization:

a. Mycoplasma testing:

Samples were prepared according to the guidelines of the service provider (Eurofins) and were submitted for Mycoplasma testing by PCR. Furthermore, media was visually monitored for bacterial contaminations after culturing without antibiotics. We tested 517 out of the 563 (92%) generated KO cell lines and did not identify any mycoplasma contaminations.

b. RNA-seq:

For transcriptomics analysis, 5×10^5 cells of each KO clone were seeded in two wells of a 12-well dish 24 hours prior to sample preparation. RNA was purified in replicates using a Qiagen 96 RNA purification kit (with on column DNase digestion) at CeMM and sent for library generation and deep sequencing on a NovaSeq machine at Boehringer Ingelheim.

To this date, we sequenced two KO clones in replicates for 216 targets. For 51 more targets, cell lysates or RNA samples have been prepared and are waiting for sequencing. For the remaining 32 targets, RNA samples still need to be prepared.

To characterize the transcriptional profile of these KO clones, RNA-seq data of two KO clones and two WT controls cells transduced with a Renilla gRNA were used to quantify endogenous transcripts. Differential expression of genes was determined using DESeq2. This analysis revealed several transcriptional responses that could be clearly assigned to SLC function and allowed phenotypical clustering of several targets. We believe that these data represent a unique opportunity to systematically study the impact of the SLC transporter activity on the transcriptional profile of the cell.

Results

The generated KO cell lines proved to be of high value for the RESOLUTE consortium and are used for assay development, transcriptomics, binder generation and validation, and genetic interaction studies. Importantly, these KO cell lines are also used to generate rescue models in the form of KO-overexpression (KO-OE) cells where the deleted target can be re-expressed in an inducible manner (reported in deliverable D1.4). We did not target SLCs that were not endogenously expressed in any of our six cancer cell lines since a KO model would not be possible in these cases. For these targets, we rely on HEK293 JumpIn overexpression cell lines (reported in D1.5). This left us with a total of 342 SLCs that could be targeted for KO models. Of those, 15 were exclusively expressed in one of the SK-MEL-28 or MDA-MB-468 cell lines which turned out to be nearly impossible to subclone in a high-throughput set-up. For another eight targets, we unable to identify any KO

clones despite validated gRNAs and genetic screens later confirmed that these SLCs are essential. For 299 of the remaining 319 targets (Figure 1), we were able to generate at least one KO clone (at least two KO clones for 279 targets). Finally, single-cell clones for the remaining 20 targets as well as the targets where only one KO clone could be retrieved so far have already been prepared and will be genotyped by the end of 2021. We expect that this will result in KO clones for another 10-15 targets.

Figure 1: KO cell line generation progress.

Discussion

The main advantage of the KO cell models over OE models is that no artificial SLC expression which may lead to functional artefacts (e.g., by mislocalization or too high levels of protein) is required. In this sense comparing KO and WT cells is still the gold standard to study a proteins cellular function.

However, it needs to be considered that prolonged culture of the KO clones (which is necessary to expand the clones from single cells) may lead to transcriptional, metabolic, or other cellular changes to compensate the SLC loss. While these effects may also lead to new insights into the targeted SLC, it becomes more challenging to study the intrinsic function of the deleted SLC. Moreover, single-cell clones derived from a parental cancer cell line which has been passaged over a long time are likely to phenotypically differ from the original cell line as well as other derived WT and KO clones due to clonal variation. It is therefore crucial to consider this variation for all observed effects.

Conclusion

The aim to generate and characterize KO cell lines for 300 SLCs has been reached.

Repository for primary data

The monoclonal KO generation process is labour intensive and usually takes several months for a single target. This is reflected by the high costs of KO clones that are generated and distributed by commercial providers. By optimizing our pipelines and processing many targets in parallel in the individual steps of the workflow, we are now able to generate KO clones for about 20 different targets per month. While we are performing an extensive characterisation of these cell lines it will not be possible to exhaust the full potential of these reagents by the RESOLUTE consortium alone. It is therefore crucial for the long-term impact of RESOLUTE that the research community has access to these cell lines. The consortium approved the distribution of HCT116 KO clones to non-RESOLUTE organizations in September 2020.

We decided to deposit all generated HCT116 KO clones (approximately 350 after completion) at the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC), one of the leading non-profit distributors of cell lines and other biological materials for research and development. Apart from the reputation and visibility of ATCC as well as their ability to ship cell lines to research institutes world-wide, we selected this distributor because it holds the licence of the HCT116 cell line. Therefore, no additional licencing or fees are required for recipients of these cell lines and the costs will be comparable to the parental HCT116 cell line (~400 USD for recipients in the US, ~600 Euro for

recipients in Europe). For all KO clones that have not been generated in HCT116, we are aiming to identify a suitable repository in 2022.

So far, we deposited 30 KO clones at ATCC which will be available to the public in 2022. Furthermore, CeMM is able to directly share HCT116 KO clones for research purpose as long resources for the distribution are available. Before any cell line can be shared by CeMM or distributed by ATCC, interested parties need to sign an MTA regulating the use of the cell lines.

RNA-seq data will be made available to the public via the RESOLUTE web portal after the corresponding data release has been approved by the consortium partners (planned for spring 2022). RNA-seq data will in addition be deposited at the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA).

The RESOLUTE web portal will provide an overview on the KO cell lines and will also allow to download sequencing results (raw data) for all experiments. Transcript and gene quantification (processed data) as well as the results of the differential expression analyses (analysed data) will be not only available for download in tabular format but can also be interactively explored via a dashboard visualization.